

MACROPHAGE ACTIVATION SYNDROME-A RARE CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT:

Hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH) is a rare, life-threatening syndrome in which abnormal immune activation causes excessive inflammation and tissue destruction. The term macrophage activation syndrome (MAS) is used when HLH occurs in the setting of systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis (SJIA, formerly known as Still's disease), adult-onset Still's disease, or other rheumatic diseases. We present the case of an 7-year-old boy with a history of sJIA who was admitted to the hospital with fever, myalgia, and arthralgia. At presentation, initial evaluation suggested that the sepsis was likely caused by acute pyelonephritis, and the patient was started on antibiotics and intravenous fluids. However, further testing revealed that her symptoms were not contagious and were likely caused by MAS, a rare complication of sJIA. We diagnosed him quickly, he was administered steroids and he recovered successfully.

INTRODUCTION

Hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH) is a rare, life-threatening syndrome in which abnormal immune activation causes excessive inflammation and tissue destruction [1].

Macrophage activation syndrome (MAS) is used when HLH occurs in the setting of systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis (SJIA, formerly known as Still's disease), adult-onset Still's disease (AOSD), or other rheumatic diseases. MAS typically occurs within the first week after onset of rheumatic disease, but may occur at any stage of the disease course [1]. This syndrome is typically characterized by fever, elevated ferritin levels, elevated acute inflammatory markers, cytopenias, and hepatosplenomegaly with concomitant underlying disease. We report a case of MAS as a rare complication of systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis [1].

CASE REPORT

A 7-year-old boy was admitted to the OPD with severe polyarticular arthralgia accompanied by fever for the past 15 days. On admission, vital signs were normal except for a temperature of 101.5°F. All tests were sent, including complete blood count, C-reactive protein, liver function tests, kidney function tests, blood culture and sensitivity, urine culture and sensitivity, dengue NS1 and Igm, Chikangunya IgG and IgM. Of all these studies, only C-reactive protein was at higher levels, i.e. >200.

Laboratory results were as follows: white blood cells 3.8 U/L, alanine transaminase 16.29 units/l. Immunological tests showed antinuclear antibody (ANA), homogeneous sample 1358 (normal = 0-49 1/dilution), spotty ANA sample 4852 (normal = 0-49 1/dilution), anti-dsDNA antibody 355 IU/ml. Tested positive for. (normal = 0-99 IU/ml), antihistone antibody 210 U/ml (normal = 0-99 U/ml), serum complement C3 35 mg/dl, serum C4 9 mg/dl.

An ASO titer and throat swab culture were then sent to rule out acute rheumatic fever, which were negative. A TB workup was performed, including sputum testing for CBNAAT and ESR, of which CBNAAT was negative and ESR was >140.

After eliminating all these serious doubts, juvenile idiopathic arthritis was suspected. Then serum lactate dehydrogenase, serum ferritin, and serum procalcitonin were sent. Ferritin on Wednesday was >1650ng/ml (normal level 22-232ng/ml), average was 1650ng/ml. LDH was 2800 IU/L (normal level is 150-300 IU/L).

An abdominal ultrasound was also performed, which revealed lymphadenopathy.

Elevated Sr.ferritin levels along with ultrasound findings indicate a diagnosis of macrophage activation syndrome. Bone marrow biopsy showed increased numbers of macrophages with hemophagocytosis suggestive of MAS. The presence of fever, cytopenia, increased ferritin, low NK cell activity, increased soluble IL-2 receptors, and hemophagocytic cells in the bone marrow and lymph nodes led to a primary diagnosis of MAS according to HLH criteria.⁵

DISCUSSION

MAS belongs to the group of hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH), which includes familial HLH and secondary HLH. The association between HLH and autoimmune or

autoinflammatory diseases is officially called MAS [2]. MAS is commonly associated with sJIA [2], but Kawasaki disease, adult Still's disease, rheumatoid arthritis, Sjögren's syndrome, dermatomyositis, mixed connective tissue disease, systemic sclerosis, and SLE have also been reported. [3].

Diagnosing MAS is difficult. In fact, the clinical features of MAS-related SLE and active SLE are very similar. A recent paper reported that 75% of patients presented with respiratory symptoms, jaundice, and lymphadenopathy [4]. However, hyperferritinemia is considered the best parameter to distinguish active sJIA from MAS-related sJIA, with a sensitivity and specificity of almost 100% [5]. However, in cases of severe leukopenia, clinicians should evaluate the presence of MAS [6]. In our patient, the diagnosis of sJIA associated with MAS was made according to the HLH-2004 criteria (see HLH criteria) [7].

HLH criteria (at least 5 criteria for diagnosis of MAS): body temperature 38.5°C for at least 7 days, splenomegaly, hypertriglyceridemia ($>160^{\circ}\text{C}$ mg/dL), hypofibrinogenemia (<2400 IU/ml, decreased NK OR Absent) cellular activity, hemophagocytic cells in the bone marrow, spleen, or lymph nodes, cytopenias in two or more cell lines (hemoglobin).

So far, the pathogenesis of MAS is not fully understood. It is thought to have a strong antiinflammatory effect, resulting from a significant disruption of the interaction between macrophages and lymphocytes, leading to an increase in the level of various cytokines, in particular TNF-

α , M-CSF receptors, interleukin- (IL) 1, IL6 and interferon gamma (IFN) gamma [8]. In this case, it would be beneficial to start immunomodulatory treatment even in the face of the disease. Today, there are many types of treatment, including non-chemical and biological treatment. The cornerstone is represented by steroids. The most common treatment is treatment of MAS

with methylprednisolone (e.g., 30 mg/kg for three consecutive days), followed by 2–3 mg/kg per day [7]. However, there are many medications that can be used alone or in combination to reduce steroid use. If there is no improvement with methylprednisolone, parenteral administration of cyclosporine A (CSA) (2–

7 mg/kg/day) is usually initiated [9]. Additionally, patients use CSA to manage MAS after discharge [5]. The HLH2004 treatment plan is beneficial for patients unresponsive to steroids and CSA [2]. Medications include dexamethasone, CSA, and etoposide. However, the potential hepatotoxicity of etoposide limits the use of these treatments. Recently, Coca et al. reported the use of antithymocyte globulin (ATG) as an alternative to etoposide [14], but anti-infusion therapy with ATG is frequently described in the literature [10]. Although some authors have reported improvement in HLH after the use of TNF-

α antagonists [11, 12], infliximab may be an effective treatment for refractory MAS patients [13]. Rituximab [14] and intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) [15] have been used with good results to treat MAS caused by viruses such as EBV or cytomegalovirus. In the pediatric field, IL-

1 blockade has become the standard of care for the treatment of MAS regardless of the underlying autoimmune disease [16–

20], but the role of IL1 in the pathogenesis of MAS is only partially understood. However, some authors have reported some cases of MAS caused by anakinra [19, 20].

CONCLUSION

Macrophage activation syndrome is a serious and life-threatening complication of several rheumatic diseases in children. Key features include persistent fever, lymphadenopathy, hepatomegaly, cytopenia, and marked hyperferritinemia. Early diagnosis and prompt treatment are the keys to treatment. Consensus criteria for the diagnosis of MAS in the context of sJIA would be helpful in this process. First-line treatment includes multicenter supportive care and high-dose corticosteroids with the addition of cyclosporine if there is no rapid response to initial treatment. In refractory cases, etoposide or antithymocyte globulin have been used, but the biologic agent anakinra is increasingly reported as the next step after steroids and cyclosporine.

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